

FOODITY News

August 2023
Vol. 1

Funded by
the European Union

**OPEN CALL #1
LAUNCH DATE**

5

September 2023

**We will launch our
1st open call on 5
September 2023!**

Participants will receive up to **187.500€**, technical support, business mentoring, group coaching and training to develop their solutions. In total, we will invest 2M€ in our pilot development programme.

[Learn more](#)

Keep up with our updates!

[/company/foodity-eu](#) [@FOODITY_EU](#) [@Data4FoodCluster](#) [rebrand.ly/FOODITY-newsletter](#)

Empowering citizens to take control of their food and nutrition data for a better future

FOODITY is an impact-driven project funded under the Horizon Europe programme. Over the next three years (2023 – 2026), we aim to create a dynamic European ecosystem of **digital solutions for food and nutrition that respect citizens' rights to personal data sovereignty**.

**OPEN CALL #1
LAUNCH DATE**

5

September 2023

 We will launch two open calls – the first on 5 September 2023 – to fund 12 industry and research collaborations for data-driven innovations in food and nutrition.

In total, we will invest **2M€** in the pilot development programme we will run, to which selected participants – from research and technology organisations and universities to SMEs, startups, social innovation actors and training organisations – will have access.

In particular, our FOODITY innovators will receive:

- Up to 187.500€
- Technology access and technical support
- Business mentoring and group coaching
- Training on technical, business, and legal matters

Are you up for the challenge?

Stay tuned to our channels for updates on how to apply!

[Learn more about our open calls](#)

Dive into our open calls pre-launch session

Open Call #1 - Summary
Key things to remember

- Timeline**
Open Call launches
5 September 2023
closes
8 November 2023
- Team**
2-3 entities
led by an SME
+
RTO / Social Innovation Actor
- Scope**
Data-driven solution in the
food and nutrition domains
+
respectful of personal data
sovereignty

Stay tuned to FOODITY.eu for the launch and info about upcoming webinars!

Important note: final and binding open call conditions will be provided in the official documentation

FOODITY

Participants in sidebar:
InoSense
Teresa
Samuel Almeida (FOODITY)
Maja - DRG4Food
Tina Jelenić (FOODITY)
Lai Hermien
Giacomo Sin

On 4 July, we held an open calls pre-launch online session together with our sister project, [DRG4FOOD](#).

Both our projects will provide almost **€4M in equity-free funding**, resources and support to food innovators to accelerate the transformation of our food and nutrition systems.

Our project coordinator, Samuel Almeida, and Maja Fišić, from DRG4FOOD, explained our calls and answered questions from participants.

[Watch the recording](#)

Meet our FOODITY team

Our ambitious project brings together seven multidisciplinary partners from seven different EU member states.

7 partners · 7 countries

From top-level experts in ICT-based solutions for the food and nutrition sector (CERTH), technologies for user's control of personal data (JIBE) and integration of data commons into federated infrastructure (SOFTEAM), to experienced professionals in engaging citizens (F6S, AUSTRALO and SPLORO) and social innovation (ZSI).

[Get to know us](#)

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